

Storied Statistics: Behind the Numbers of Indonesian Mecca Pilgrims (1851–2016)

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Abstract

This article examines the historical dataset of Indonesian pilgrims traveling to Mecca between 1851 and 2016 to reflect upon the epistemological and political dimensions of quantification. Drawing on debates in digital humanities, it argues that quantitative historical data, and statistics in particular, are neither self-evident nor neutral but deeply embedded in changing worldviews and governance practices. Using the concept of “storied statistics”, the study discusses how colonial authorities monitored the Hajj pilgrimage to prevent anti-colonial sentiment, later reframing it as an indicator of prosperity. The dataset is situated within a broader research agenda on sustainability and well-being, using the Dutch CBS Monitor as a heuristic model to explore historical developments. By tracing the entanglement of Hajj statistical records with colonial and post-colonial agendas, the article argues that historical quantitative data must be treated qualitatively.

Keywords: historical quantitative data, storied statistics, colonial datasets, Indonesia, Mecca pilgrimage, Hajj

1. Introduction

At her recent valedictory lecture, historian of technology Ruth Oldenziel reminded the audience that there is no such thing as self-evident or self-explanatory data: data need stories; however, she added, stories could also do with data (Oldenziel 2025). What Oldenziel wished to highlight was the fact that quantification must not be considered a prerogative of objectivity, in the same way that qualification should not promptly equate subjectivity. This issue has been discussed for some time in the context of digital humanities, namely under new concept proposals such as Johanna Drucker's "capta" instead of data, aiming to highlight agency in the production of data rather than the conflation of the phenomenon itself in its recorded observation (Drucker 2011); or Matthew Lavin's counter proposal of "situated data", defending that digital humanists should "use the word *data* mindfully and unapologetically based on the understanding that data are collected, assembled and recorded by people (or their instruments)" (Lavin 2025). In other contexts, data uncertainties and limitations —i.e. the need of further explanation, contextualization, or, one could also say, *stories*—have been discussed both regarding historical "hard" data (meaning, according to the authors, "readily observable and quantifiable" data, more connected to the natural sciences) and historical "soft" data (attributed to the social sciences). Here, however, the framing of the issue leans into problematizing the long-term historical aspect (multi-centennial timescales), rather than the data per se (Van Bavel et al. 2019).

These are, in fact, two different issues that are equally important when thinking about data of the past. Not only was this data "taken", or "produced", rather than "given", but it was taken and produced by historical actors which lived, communicated and created

meaning within a different worldview system, or a different *episteme*, the term Michel Foucault used to describe a language spoken unconsciously in a specific period of history (Krauss 2011, 15–16). There is maybe not a better example of such critical entanglement as in the case of historical statistics. Etymologically derived from the Latin *statisticum collegium* (“council of state”), the designation also incorporated the meaning of the 18th century German term *Statistik*,

which meant “state affairs” or “state craft” informed by a “science” of politics—meaning scientific inquiries by learned men should be undertaken to help direct the affairs of the state and develop the best kind of policies (Arneil 2020, 744).

Statistics shape as well as reinforce specific worldviews: they allow for making sense of the world, not only because they name and organize that world, but because, in doing so, they are actually creating it (Porter 1995, 21). But worldviews change over time, just as the meaning and the stories that one might connect with the numbers recorded in a historical document.

This article aims to explore the well-publicized as well as the more hidden stories connected with a specific set of numbers: the historical statistics recorded on the number of Hajj pilgrims departed from the Indonesian archipelago to Mecca between 1851 and 2016, which I have compiled from data published by the Indonesian and the Dutch national statistics offices in several formats (van Vliet 2025).¹ Working from this dataset as an example, I will argue that when working with historical quantitative datasets spanning long periods of time, it is fundamental to not only understand, but to make visible the changing historical circumstances throughout the data production process. This is particularly imperative in the case of historical data published by

¹ The dataset can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.4121/6ec9e536-afd3-468a-9ca3-8a5b5ad3c199>. The several sources are detailed in the documentation available with the dataset.

national statistics offices. On the one hand, these are often some of the more readily available materials that researchers can find, since they are archived and preserved by the state apparatus. On the other hand, the same connection to the state, and governance in particular, make this data irredeemably connected to a very specific time and historical context: statistics are gathered to monitor specific policies, to give insight into (by then) current debates, and are firmly embedded in ideological and political projects.

These concerns take on a much more crucial dimension when thinking about statistical records of colonial and post-colonial regimes, as is the case of the dataset in question. Historical anthropologist and (post)-colonial scholar Ann Laura Stoler has used the term “storied edges” to talk about the stories that can be found in the in-betweens, in the interstices of colonial archival materials: these are stories that do not fit in the established narrative of the colonial regime, but which are inadvertently preserved in the same archive (Stoler 2009, 143). Expanding on Stoler’s concept, I propose to speak of “storied statistics” when analysing the more invisible stories connected to the dataset under investigation.

2. Quantifying Well-being in the *Longue Durée*

As David Armitage and Jo Guldi so lucidly articulated, the mass retro-digitization of archival materials as well as the development of new computational methodologies created an auspicious environment for the historical disciplines to (re)turn to the project of the *longue durée*, abandoning the long trend of the microhistory perspective which had been popular in the last decades of the 20th century; furthermore, they argued, these were also favourable conditions for a much needed re-engagement of

history with ongoing public debate (Armitage and Guldi 2015; Guldi and Armitage 2014). This aspiration is an important point for the research context of the case at hand.

The Mecca pilgrims' dataset was compiled within a research project that looks at how historical metrics can provide insights into well-being and sustainability developments in connection with industrialization and extractivism in the establishment of global supply chains during the early twentieth century until the present. The STONEM project—Sustainability Trade-offs in the Netherlands' Entangled Modernization, 1900-2020²—investigates these well-being and sustainability developments in particular connected to the flow of resources between the Netherlands and the Global South, namely Indonesia.

Central to the project's approach is the Monitor Well-Being and the Sustainable Development Goals developed by CBS – Netherlands Statistics.³ The monitor is organized in three main dimensions: Here and Now, which monitors what is happening now and includes indicators such as housing costs, satisfaction with life, (healthy) life expectancy or exposure to particulate matter; the dimension Later, which comprises “savings”, the accumulation (or depletion) of capitals (divided into Economic, Natural, Human and Social capital) that future generations are estimated to have based on current spendings—examples of indicators include education level, trust in institutions, household debt or cumulative CO2 emissions; and the dimension Elsewhere, which aims

² The project is funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and based at Eindhoven University of Technology. More information can be found at <https://stonem.org/>.

³ This monitor was created from a mandate of the Dutch government and conceptualized following the recommendations of the Council for European Statisticians (CES), with the Brundtland definition of sustainable development as its foundational principle (Horlings and Smits 2019). It is based on the following definition: “Well-being concerns the quality of life here and now as well as the extent to which this quality is achieved at the expense of future generations or of people in other countries” (Horlings and Smits 2019).

to monitor the impact of the country in the well-being of people living elsewhere in the planet—with indicators such as imports of resources, land footprint or official development assistance.⁴

We want to use this monitor as a heuristic model to investigate historical sustainability trade-offs. The advantages of using this monitor as a blueprint for historical research is that it discourages cherry-picking single issues and pushes for charting and exploring historical interactions between trade and living conditions, working conditions and personal and social changes, but also environmental pressures and economic development. By consolidating economic, environmental and social concerns into a data model, the monitor also connects with environmental historian Sverker Sörlin's Anthropocene *Weltanschauung* argument, in which a data model and a particular worldview embody and reinforce one another (Sörlin 2025). Furthermore, the monitor provides a helpful frame of reference, a common language to be used between policy makers, governmental bodies, the press, civil society, and academic researchers, namely historians.

The project builds on previous research that reconstructed historical monitors for the Netherlands between 1850 and 2010 (Lintsen et al. 2018). This research showed that the monitor had the potential not only for conveying long-term dynamics, but also for making visible changes in the social agenda over time, in terms of what is important for historical societies. For instance, while extreme poverty was a concern of late nineteenth century Dutch society, climate pressures and natural environments are the most

⁴ The monitor is published annually on the website of Statistics Netherlands. See, for example, the 2025 Monitor at <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/visualisations/monitor-of-well-being-and-the-sustainable-development-goals>.

important topics today. And these are not independent developments: while industrialization helped lift populations from poverty, it did so at the costs of the environment (Smits and Lintsen 2018).

While the monitor was originally created for the Netherlands, its focus on the Brundtland definition of sustainable development, as well as its support of the proposals of the Council for European Statisticians (CES) and its alignment with the United Nations SDG's, make for convincing arguments that could support, theoretically, the adoption of this model to monitor well-being and sustainability in other parts of the world. My idea was to try to reconstruct an historical monitor for Indonesia, at sub-national level; my motivations included wanting to try to “flip the monitor”, so to speak, in order to give center stage to the periphery (from the perspective of the Netherlands) and to place the Netherlands in the Elsewhere dimension of the monitor. My first step, then, was to explore and locate historical data that I could use as relevant indicators for the thematic sections of the monitor.

3. Historical Statistics and Big Data of the Past

Datafication has been defined as the process of putting a phenomenon in quantified form so that it can be analysed and tabulated, as well as a kind of dematerialization that converts natural phenomena into symbolic material that can be indexed and searched. It is usually associated with the most recent stage of digitalization, where big data and algorithms are used for “quantifying life” through digital information, often for economic purposes (Wickberg et al. 2024, 2).

The process of datafication and quantification is central to the well-being and sustainable development monitor. But while digital technology was instrumental to create the *datafied* world of the present, data streams of different yet considerable sizes

have existed for a very long time. In fact, as digital humanists Frederic Kaplan and Isabella di Leonardo have argued, one might even be able to talk about *Big Data of the Past* (2017).

Kaplan and di Leonardo claim that data acceleration regimes can be found in ancient cities of Mesopotamia, where administrative documents were produced on argyle tablets, compiling information on economic, diplomatic and commercial exchanges. Thousands of years later, nineteenth century industrialization saw the rise of information tracking systems such as the cadaster or the census. According to the authors, the fundamental characteristic of any historical recording technology that makes one able to talk about data acceleration, is

their capacity to deal with an open-ended stream of information and reorganize it to fit a given information paradigm, creating new relationships between them: we call them regulated representations. (...) man-made material documents governed by a set of production and usage rules, that stand for something else, typically a complex event or phenomenon (2017, 4).

With the well-being and sustainability model functioning as our current information paradigm, it was upon this regulated representation—organized in dimensions, themes and indicators—that I aimed to, in Kaplan and Di Leonardo's terms, to “redocument the past”, which implies recollection (choosing and rejecting data, which will produce distortions by amplifying certain issues and diminishing others) and remapping (bending the historical data to fit the current regulated representation) (2017, 8). But these, eventual, current transformations must nevertheless contend with distortions not made by the present paradigms, but by the historical paradigms that shaped their production. And with this I particularly mean one spectacularly prolific data acceleration regime: colonialism.

Colonialism and statistics have an entangled history: they could further the “principle of improvement” of nineteenth century social reform ideals; as well as to be used to identify “deviations from the norm” as “deviations from the mean” (Arneil 2020, 751; Stoler 2009, 30). Furthermore, numbers could convey a semblance of objectivity and fairness, speak the universalist language of Empire, all while providing authority to governing bodies (Porter 1995).

The first efforts to produce statistics by colonial administrators in the Netherlands Indies date back to the early nineteenth century: these efforts aimed to understand what could be subject to taxation and focused only on the island of Java (Van der Eng 1996). With the creation of specialized departments in the colonial administrative structure from 1855 onwards—departments of Finance, Public Works, Education, Religion and Industry, Justice, and, Agriculture—the production of statistics became their own responsibility. This gathered information was fundamental for the creation of a “paper colony” that could be ruled directly from the metropole, in The Hague (Jeurgens 2015). The data collected by these administrative departments was published in Colonial Reports and also added to the Dutch Annual Statistical Yearbook published by the CBS. By 1925, the mandate to produce colonial statistics grew to such an extent that a centralized office was created in Weltevreden, a suburb of Batavia, now Jakarta: the Centraal Kantoor voor de Statistiek (CKS). By 1941, 700 people worked at the CKS (Van der Eng 1996). During the Japanese occupation and later the war for independence, data collection was intermittent. After independence, the CKS merged with the Kantor Penjelidikan Oemoem (KPO) and formed the Kantor Pusat Statistik (KPS), under the department of economic affairs. By the 1960s, with the mandate to produce population

census and directly responsible to the Indonesian government, the independent institution Biro Pusat Statistik (BPS) was created. This institution is currently responsible for the collection of national statistics in Indonesia.

I focused my research for historical data on these two institutions: the current national statistics office of Indonesia, and the historical archive of the colonial statistics preserved by the Dutch national statistics office.⁵ At first, I was able to gather a significant amount of data and to map this data into the monitor: in particular the theme structure of the model, more than at individual indicator level, could be somewhat kept. Yet, most of these data streams were quite recent, at best going as far as the 1990s. Working with earlier datasets implied further recollection and remapping of data in what concerns changing geographic borders and aggregation levels, and that was only in the case I could find indicators which I could eventually collate. Even fundamental time series such as population size at regional level could be quite challenging: here not only border changes but interest of the colonial administration in certain areas to the detriment of others – for instance gathering detailed information for the island of Java, but aggregating the vast rest of the territory into the category “Outer Provinces” – created great disparities in data streams. However, I was able to track down one specific data stream that I could trace somewhat consistently (though with some gaps) since the mid-nineteenth until the twentieth century: the number of Hajj pilgrims departed to Mecca from the Indonesian Archipelago, per province, with details for the Outer Provinces as well.

⁵ And publicly available via their website: <https://historisch.cbs.nl/>

4. Public Stories & Hidden Stories

Thus, how can this data be interpreted and is there a place for this indicator in the well-being and sustainability monitor? The dataset seems to be misleadingly straightforward: as seen in the simple line graph visualization in Figure 1, there is an overall increase in number of pilgrims, very likely to be interpreted in line with population growth and increasing material welfare. Following the same line of thought, falling or low numbers seem to be able to be attributed to external factors such as the first and second world wars. Additionally, differences between provinces seem to offer a window for comparisons, with population size and socio-economic factors as possible productive aspects to inform the comparative analysis. This is certainly one strategy to look at these numbers. But in what other ways can this data be interpreted? What other aspects, intrinsic to these numbers can be considered? For instance, why were these numbers recorded in the colonial archive in the first place?

Fig 1. Visualization of the dataset, color coded by province.

The Dutch colonial authorities eyed the Hadj with the suspicion of instigating anti-colonial sentiments since the beginning of the nineteenth century: as such “pilgrimage was to be made difficult, not to be prohibited” (Vredembregt 1962, 99). One way to try to discourage the pilgrimage was to create administrative obstacles around it: in other words, papers, produced by the colonial administration, required by the aspiring pilgrim, and ready to be included in the statistics shipped to The Hague. As early as 1825, the Governor General of the Dutch East Indies published issued an ordinance which required pilgrims to request permission and the payment of a large fee before being able to travel to Mecca (Jeurgens 2015). However, this ordinance applied only to Java and Madura, so many pilgrims escaped the fee (and the statistics) by travelling via Sumatra. In the new ordinance of 1859, the tax was abolished, but the paper trail requirement was preserved: aspiring pilgrims had to prove to the Dutch authorities that they were in possession of the necessary funds and that their families and dependents could be provided for in their absence, and only then travel documents were issued; furthermore, an examination was to be made upon their return, and only then were the pilgrims allowed to make use of the title of “Hadji” (Vredembregt 1962). This means that while the Dutch colonial authorities aimed to discourage the pilgrimage, they also aimed to limit the use of the newly acquired social status of the returned pilgrim.

According to missionary, linguist and ethnologist Carel Poensen, writing in the 1880s,

The Hadji feels like a different man; he has ceased to be Javanese, he is Hadji! By means of the pilgrimage Islam has made him into a citizen of the world!⁶

⁶ Cited in (Jeurgens 2015, 115)

Social mobility is an important aspect to consider when looking at this dataset. There is some evidence that, in addition to gaining a higher standard and the respect of one's community, returning pilgrims were found to have acquired a new and strong entrepreneurial spirit, with examples of expanding agricultural estates and new business ventures into moneylending. Dutch anthropologist Jacob Vredembregt argues that the Hadj could then be seen as an emancipatory element in the formation of the Indonesian middle class by the beginning of the twentieth century (1962, 117). Other Dutch scholars had diverging opinions: a certain Friedrich Zeilinger, writing in his doctoral dissertation published in 1933, argued that the pilgrimage was a negative influence in terms of financial capital formation of the indigenous population, since considerable savings would be spent on this journey (Zeilinger 1933). Zeilinger frames the Hadj not as an indicator of social mobility and emancipation, but as an indicator of (or lack thereof) economic welfare. This was certainly also a factor for the colonial administration as the statistical reports of the 1930s include a detailed overview of the pilgrimage costs, even though the accuracy of the numbers is put into question by the producers themselves: with an average cost given as 975 guilders (almost 12 000 euros today⁷), this amount is qualified with the accompanying sentence: "as a rule this amount is surpassed even mani- and tenfold" (Centraal Kantoor voor de Statistiek 1932, 115). It is nevertheless important to note that the pilgrimage was also a good business opportunity for the Dutch, more specifically to the Dutch shipping companies which transported the pilgrims and often required the purchase of return-tickets (Ray 2023).

⁷ This value was calculated with the CBS tool available at <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/prijzen-toen-en-nu> .

But besides social and economic aspects, the Hadj was also framed as an important indicator of non-material prosperity. This was done by none other than historical actors connected to the Dutch government at the height of the Indonesian revolutionary wars. In a publication titled *The Netherlands and Indonesia: Through Cooperation towards Prosperity and Development*, the number of Hadj pilgrims is interpreted as a less fallible prosperity indicator than the financial estimates regarding the income of the Indonesian population (Haccou 1947). But this must be seen also with an additional perspective since Indonesian revolutionaries framed the pilgrimage as “political escapism”, besides potentially leading to a higher levels of poverty (Vredembregt 1962). In fact, after Indonesian independence, legal restrictions were also created regarding the Hadj. Importantly, the Indonesian government introduced a quota system per province (totaling 10.00 for the whole country in 1950), as well as laws that prevented citizens from selling specific sorts of personal estate in order to finance it, namely rice-fields. In the late 1980s, a quota system was also introduced by the government of Saudi Arabia and agreed by the Organization of Islamic Cooperation Summit in 1987; this quota system is still in use today and it is calculated according to each country’s Muslim population, by a factor of 1 pilgrim per 1000 Muslims. Indonesia, with the world’s largest Muslim population has a quota of 221.000 pilgrims per year, but waiting lists can still be very long, with some estimates between 11 and 47 years (Istahar et al. 2024).

The multiple perspectives on the Hajj dataset discussed above suggest that this indicator is relevant for discussing of the historical well-being of Indonesians. However, rather than being tied to a single theme, it appears to encompass a wide range of issues. In other words, these numbers reflect several dimensions: surveillance and control—embedded in a regulatory legal framework—by the colonial administration, later echoed

in the introduction of quotas by the postcolonial government and international regulatory bodies; social status and mobility, as the pilgrimage was perceived to contribute to the emergence of an Indonesian middle class; and, prominently, an economic dimension, even though its framing varied across time and among historical actors within the same period. Ultimately, rather than fitting neatly within a specific monitoring theme, the number of Hajj pilgrims functions as a kind of “mini-monitor,” offering a lens through which to examine economic, social, and institutional developments that shaped the well-being of the Indonesian population since the mid-nineteenth century.

5. Conclusion

Quantification is something we do, it is a performative action, not a descriptive action. Statistics help make sense of the world, because they structure, organize and classify an otherwise messy and complex world. Echoing Sörlin, data scientist Hanna Davis argues “a dataset is a worldview” (2020). But while Sörlin is referring to a data model that encapsulates the issues of current debates, Davis is talking about the subjectivity of the people behind the numbers as she proposes that datasets should have expiration dates. Her argument is that datasets carry the bias of their conditions of production, and as ideas, tools and procedures change, they might not be fit for consumption anymore; this is particularly relevant in the case of machine learning use or when there is not an interrogation on the perceived *objectivity* of the data.

This is, of course, particularly critical in terms of colonial data. Digital historians are well aware of the challenges to decolonize the archive (Zaagsma 2023). And specific proposals such as Data Envelopes for Cultural Heritage Data provide important frameworks to reflect upon the positionality of the stakeholders involved in creating meaning from archival materials, from historical producers to contemporary annotators (Eskevich and Luthra 2024). However, this perspective must be applied not only to qualitative but also to quantitative historical data, such as statistics produced for purposes of (colonial) administration and governance. What was measured, how it was measured, the categories, classifications, and level of detail were all determined by the concerns and priorities of historical political regimes. These datasets reflect the worldview of their producers—and how that worldview evolved over time. The Mecca Pilgrims dataset is a particularly illustrative example of the multiple narratives behind the numbers: these figures are not only linked to economic and social developments but also reveal the shifting perspectives and public framing of their colonial producers, moving from a tool of surveillance and control to an indicator of well-being. In fact, these historical records may tell us more about the people who created them than about the phenomenon they sought to represent.

Contemporary public debate thrives on numbers and quantification. But according to Armitage and Guldi, historians might be partly to blame for this state of affairs: retreating to microhistory, they “stopped writing for the institutions of the world government” and “economists took their place” (2015, 237). Returning to the public arena, the historian must be able to, in the words of Ruth Oldenziel, put forth “the poetry of data and the precision of stories” (2025). Because, contrary to prevailing assumptions, the boundary between quantitative and qualitative inquiry—between

numbers and stories—is not as rigid as it is often framed. As data scholar Jacqueline Wernimont reminds us,

(...) those who work regularly with quantifications understand the paradox that the ultimate test of quantitative methods and results... is not quantitative, but qualitative: do the numbers give us something we can work with?(2021, 430)

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